

A Tracer Study on the 2021 to 2023 Rizal Technological University Psychology Graduates

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ABSTRACT

Psychology plays a vital role in society by delving into the human mind and behavior. Psychologists contribute significantly to various fields. In this context, the Psychology program of Rizal Technological University stands as a major contributor to the development of qualified professionals equipped to address the various needs of society. By examining the real-world experiences and professional trajectories of graduates, tracer studies also provide a crucial link between theory and practice. This study aims to trace the career paths and outcomes of Rizal Technological University Bachelor of Science in Psychology graduates from 2021 to 2023. The study utilized a quantitative-descriptive approach, and data were gathered using a survey anchored to the Graduate Tracer Survey of CHED. Findings revealed that most respondents were from the 2022 batch, and most currently reside in cities. A significant majority (87%) of respondents are employed, with most (78.7%) holding regular or permanent positions. A large portion of respondents (71.9%) are working within the field of Psychology, mostly industrial, with many employed in rank-and-file positions. It can be concluded that the Psychology program at Rizal Technological University is relevant to the respondent's current jobs. Findings indicate that the Psychology program at Rizal Technological University can prepare its graduates to perform effectively within their job environment and make worthwhile contributions to their organizations and communities. Lastly, it can be concluded that there are significant differences in the developed skills and learned competencies of the respondents in the psychology program when grouped according to their employment status.

Keywords: *Tracer Study, Psychology, Graduate Tracer Survey*

1. Introduction

Psychology plays a vital role in society. By delving into the human mind and behavior, psychologists contribute significantly to various fields. From mental health treatment to education and marketing, the influence of psychology is undeniable. In this context, the Psychology program¹⁵⁷ of Rizal Technological University stands as a major contributor to the development of qualified professionals equipped to address the various needs of society. However, a comprehensive evaluation is necessary to fully comprehend the program's effectiveness and its graduates' ultimate impact.

The Commission on Higher Education issued Memorandum Order No. 19, Series of 2012-Criterion 8, requiring graduate tracer studies (GTS) to trace whether an alumnus is employed, has received award(s) or recognition(s), and has held management positions in government, industries, and companies within the last five years. This initiative aims to raise academic standards and create new learning and development opportunities for Filipino students.

This study aims to trace the career paths and outcomes of Rizal Technological University Bachelor of Science in Psychology graduates from batches 2021 to 2023 and to assess if there are significant differences in the developed skills and learned competencies of the respondents in the psychology program when grouped according to their employment status.

Tracer studies represent a well-established research methodology within the field of higher education. Tracer studies involve tracking graduates after a designated period, typically one to five years after graduation, to gather valuable data on their employment status, career progression, and the overall efficacy of their academic preparation.

By examining the real-world experiences and professional trajectories of graduates, tracer studies also provide a crucial link between theory and practice. This tracer study on the 2021 to 2023 Rizal Technological University Psychology graduates seeks to bridge this gap. It will delve into the graduates' experiences, exploring how the program's curriculum equipped them with the necessary competencies and developed their skills to navigate the complexities of the professional world. By analyzing their employment data, the study will offer valuable insights into the effectiveness of the Psychology program, and by examining the journeys of the 2021 to 2023 graduates, the study can illuminate potential areas for program improvement, ensuring that future graduates are equipped to serve society as well-rounded and impactful psychology professionals.

2. Methods

The study utilized a quantitative approach to trace the career paths and outcomes of the 2021–2023 psychology graduates from Rizal Technological University—Boni and Pasig. Creswell (2013) defines quantitative research methodology as a “mean of testing objective theories by examining the relationship among the variables. These variables, in turn, can be measured, typically on instruments, so that numbered data can be analyzed using statistical procedures.”

Furthermore, the study used a descriptive method to paint a statistical portrait of the respondents' personal and educational background, employment data, and the advanced studies and training they attended after college. Ethridge (2004) states that it is characterized as an attempt to describe, determine, and put in order the data in research studies.

2.1 Population Frame and Sampling Scheme

Bachelor of Science in Psychology graduates from both Boni Campus and Pasig Campus from 2021 to 2023 were selected using Quota Sampling as the respondents to this study. According to Fleetwood (2023), quota sampling, also called the combination of stratified and convenience sampling, is a non-probability sampling technique where researchers select a convenience sample of people representative of the population. Researchers selected these people based on certain characteristics. For the market research samples to be helpful in gathering data, they determine and set quotas. These samples can be generalized to the entire population. The researchers were able to select a sample of one hundred (100) out of the eight hundred thirty-eight graduates from 2021-2023.

2.2 Description of the Respondents

The respondents of this study are the 2021–2023 graduates of Rizal Technological University who completed the psychology program. Respondents were selected with the help of the RTU Office of the Student and Alumni Affairs Services Facebook page.

2.3 Research Instrument Used

An online survey questionnaire anchored to the Graduate Tracer Survey (GTS) developed by the Commission on Higher Education (CHED) was utilized to gather data on the respondents' personal and educational background, employment data, the training and advanced studies they attended after college, and the relevance of the curriculum of the psychology program to their employment. The survey was administered through Google Forms.

2.4 Data Gathering Procedure

To collect data, the researchers utilized the lists of graduates from 2021-2023 posted in the RTU Office of the Student and Alumni Affairs Services' Facebook page. The researchers used this directory to select graduates from the Boni and Pasig campuses. The researchers utilized Google Forms to administer the online survey. Informed consent was sought before the survey was administered. The respondents were assured that the information they supplied in the survey questionnaire would be treated with the utmost care and confidentiality. Ethical considerations will undoubtedly be used throughout the study, and respondents will not be forced to complete the questionnaire and may discontinue their participation; upon doing so, the collected data will be deleted.

2.5 Statistical Treatment of Data

Simple descriptive statistics. Used to summarize and organize the respondents' personal and educational background, training(s), advanced studies pursued after college, and employment data in frequency and percent distribution tables. As stated by Hayes (2024), descriptive statistics is used to summarize the data and frequency distributions and identify the characteristics of the data set through the summaries of the sample and its measures.

Weighted Mean and Standard Deviation. Were used to measure the relativeness of the developed skills and competencies after taking the psychology program and the relativeness of the curriculum to the actual practice.

Two-way ANOVA. Was used to determine if there are significant differences in terms of the skills developed and useful competencies learned in the psychology program when it comes to their employment.

3. Results

Table 1

Distribution of Respondents by their Demographic profile

Year Graduated	n	%
2021	3	3%
2022	42	42%
2023	55	55%
Campus		
Pasig	61	61%
Boni	36	39%
Civil Status		
Single	99	99.0%
Single parent (Not married)	1	1.0%
Sex		
Female	85	85.0 %
Male	15	15.0 %
Region		
NCR	62	62.0 %
Region 4	28	28.0 %
Region 3	4	4.0 %
Region 5	1	1.0 %
Region 6	2	2.0 %
Region 7	1	1.0 %
Region 8	1	1.0 %
Region 12	1	1.0 %

Residence

City	75	75.0%
Municipality	25	25.0%
Total	100	100%

Table 1 shows the distribution of respondents from the Rizal Technological University Psychology program who graduated between 2021 and 2023. As shown in the table, the majority of the respondents, 55%, graduated in 2023 with 55 respondents. In contrast, graduates from 2022 are 42% of the total population, with 42 people, while those from 2021 make up only 3% with only 3 individuals. With a total of 100 respondents, the study presented a clear percentage distribution.

This distribution is skewed toward more recent graduates, with more than half of the respondents from the 2023 batch. The low representation of 2021 graduates might reflect challenges in reaching older alumni or smaller cohort sizes for that year.

The distribution of respondents according to the campus where they graduated is also shown in the table. Among the 100 respondents, a total of 61 graduates (61%) were from the Pasig campus, and the remaining 39 respondents (39%) were from the Boni campus. It means that the respondents, who come from the Pasig campus, may be of a larger population size or more actively engaged alumni network, thereby making the graduates more easily accessible for the study. On the other hand, fewer respondents coming from the Boni campus may result from a smaller cohort size or difficulty in reaching the graduates.

The distribution of respondents by civil status. Among the 100 respondents, 99% were single. Only one respondent was a single parent who has borne a child but is not married. This distribution shows that almost all participants in the tracer study are unmarried with very few people with parenting responsibilities.

A high percentage of single respondents might indicate that the graduates are relatively young because the study covers recent cohorts from 2021 to 2023. People at this age usually focus on their careers or further education rather than getting married. In conclusion, it follows that this distribution highlights an overall predominance of single respondents among the Psychology graduates covered within this study.

The distribution of respondents in the graduates covered by this tracer is 100, which composed 85% females and only males composing the remaining 15% of respondents in this study, thereby representing a high number of women majority graduates from the studied Psychology programs of the Rizal Technological University in that period.

The origin of all these respondents. From it, it can be found that most of the 62 respondents accounted for 62%. Followed by Region 4 with 28, for a total of 28%. The two of which comprised 90% in total. The remaining 10% is spread among other

regions. Region 3 has 4 (4%), Region 6 has 2 (2%), and Regions 5, 7, 8, and 12 have 1 (1%) each.

This distribution indicates that most respondents are from areas near the university or urban centers, like NCR and Region 4, probably because of the proximity and accessibility of the institution to these regions. The significantly smaller representation of other regions indicates a rather limited geographic diversity of graduates covered by the study and may reflect enrollment trends or the appeal of the institution, which is primarily to students within nearby areas.

The data indicate a rather high concentration of respondents in NCR and Region 4, pointing towards the university's reach in these regions. Minimal representation in other more distant regions means an opportunity for the university to spread its influence or accessibility in other parts of the country.

On the other hand, the breakdown of respondents according to place of residence. Most respondents, 75 (75%), reside in cities; the rest, 25 respondents (25%), stay in municipalities. This simply means that most graduates targeted in the tracer study were urban dwellers, except for a quarter who dwelled in less urbanized or rural areas.

The fact that more respondents are city-based indicates that the university may be attractive to city dwellers because of its locality or accessibility to the citizens. Cities are more often accessible to higher learning and public means of transport, among other amenities. This can explain the reason why most of the students are represented by cities.

The converse is the lower proportion of municipal residents which could be due to geographical, financial, or logistical challenges associated with rural residents accessing the university.

Overall, the result points to an urban inclination among the respondents that is likely to bias the study's result concerning graduates' employment and availability since towns are areas that characteristically have greater employment rates and professional circles. As a future scope of such studies, this research will reveal whether differences exist in career outcomes among urban as opposed to rural graduates, which can explain location-based differentiation of post-graduation opportunities.

Table 2

Distribution of Respondents by Educational Attainment

Educational Attainment	Counts	% of Total
Bachelor Degree	99	99.0 %
Master's Degree	1	1.0 %

Educational Attainment	Counts	% of Total
Total	100	100.0%

The distribution of respondents by their highest educational attainment is shown in Table 2. Of the 100 respondents, 99 (99%) possess a bachelor's degree, while only one respondent (1%) has pursued and obtained a master's degree. This shows that most of the graduates covered in the study have not pursued higher education after their undergraduate degree.

The fact that there is a predominance of respondents who have a bachelor's degree conforms with the focus of this tracer study on recent graduates, who are most probably at the early stages of their careers. The master's degree graduate may be either a graduate who pursued advanced studies right after completing his bachelor's degree or returned later on to further education. The low representation of postgraduate attainment may, therefore, be taken to reflect low opportunities or motivation for further studies amongst this group of graduates, as may be related to several factors such as lack of financial resources, employment opportunities, or preference for work experience over academic progression.

Table 3

Distribution of Undergraduate Award(s) or Honor(s) the Respondents Received

Awards or Honors	Counts	% of Total
Magna Cum Laude	6	4.92%
Cum Laude	32	39.02%
Laude	1	.82%
Dean's Lister	17	20.5%
Academic Achiever	6	4.92%
Academic Scholar	1	.82%
Astral Achiever	1	.82%
Athlete of the Year	1	.82%
Sports Awardee	1	.82%
Loyalty Awardee	5	6.1%
BS Psychology Gawad Sigya Special Citation Awardee	1	.82%
Special Citation Awardee for Top Student Leaders in RTU	1	.82%
TDP Medal	2	1.64%
Cultural Award	2	1.64%
Most Outstanding Student	2	1.64%
Leadership Awardee	1	.82%

Academic Excellence Awardee	2	1.64%
Total	82	100.0

Table 3 presents the breakdown of awards or honors distributed among undergraduates. From the result, it was established that the Rizal Technological University Psychology program was able to award the students with 82 awards or honors, which can be differentiated into academic, extracurricular, and leadership achievements.

Among these, academic honors rank the highest, with the greatest number of recipients who attained the Cum Laude level of achievement (32 awards), followed by Magna Cum Laude (6 awards) and Laude (1 award). In addition, 17 respondents were placed on the Dean's List, and 6 were named Academic Achievers. These numbers reflect the academic excellence of a sizeable number of graduates.

In terms of extracurricular and leadership recognitions, several specific ones stand out, though they are fewer in frequency: Loyalty Awardees (5 recipients), Most Outstanding Student (2 recipients), Cultural Award (2 recipients), and other unique distinction awards such as the Athlete of the Year recipient (1 recipient) and Leadership Awardee recipient (1 recipient). On the other hand, some respondents received special citations for contributions toward student leadership or institutional activities, like the Special Citation Award for Top Student Leaders in RTU received by 1 respondent.

The fact that there are diverse awards suggests that the graduates' accomplishments are multi-dimensional, such that the graduates not only succeed academically but also in extracurricular and leadership endeavors. The high incidence of respondents gaining academic honors reflects strong academic pressure, but other awards exist, and they reflect something of a well-rounded profile. A very high number of respondents with academic honors implies that emphasis is primarily placed on academics within a program, and the availability of other types of honors indicates the well-rounded nature of graduates.

In conclusion, the data show a culture of excellence very much rooted in academics and, more so, fewer but still considerable leadership, cultural, and sports-related acknowledgments. This balance proves that the students have an all-round development to do well in diverse fields of study throughout undergraduate studies.

Table 4*Distribution of Respondents by the Professional Examination(s) Passed*

Professional Examinations Passed	Counts	% of Total
None yet	51	51.0 %
Psychometrician	30	30.0 %
Civil Service Professional Exam	9	9.0 %
Certified Human Resource Associate	10	10.0 %
Total	100	100.0%

The data in Table 4 shows the distribution of respondents according to the professional examinations passed. Out of 100 respondents, 51 respondents, or 51%, said they have not yet passed and/or taken any professional examination, meaning that more than half of the graduates have not acquired professional licensure or certification since graduation.

Of the respondents left, 30 were successful in the Psychometrician Licensure Examination; this is the most pertinent professional licensure among graduates in Psychology. The above proportion indicates the percentage of graduates who have applied for and been granted licensure within their profession. Moreover, 10 respondents passed the CHRA certification, which might indicate an interest in human resources and personnel management careers. Fewer respondents, at 9 percent, were recipients of Civil Service Professional Eligibility which qualifies people to work for the government. This distribution points to varied career paths after graduation, most seek certifications relevant to their educational qualifications, for instance, a Psychometrician, but others have opted for certification to enter a career away from conventional psychological careers, such as CHRA or Civil Service. The proportion of the respondents who did not sit any professional exam could represent individuals still in preparation to take an examination, others may be placed in careers where no exam is necessary, or persons who want experience over accreditation.

Table 5*Distribution of Respondents by their Reason(s) for taking the Psychology Program*

Reason(s) for Taking Exam	Counts	% of Total
High grades in the course or subject area(s) related to the course	12	12%
Good grades in High School	8	8%

Influence of Parents or Relatives	13	13%
Peer Influence	15	15%
Inspired by a role model	18	18%
Strong passion for the profession	32	32%
Prospect for immediate employment	8	8%
Status or prestige of the profession	5	5%
Availability of course offering in chosen institution	24	24%
Prospect of career advancement	17	17%
Affordable for the family	10	10%
Prospect of attractive compensation	3	3%
Opportunity for employment abroad	4	4%
No particular choice or no better idea	6	6%
Other	5	5%
Total	100	100%

The data presented in Table 5 illustrates the distribution of respondents' reasons for choosing the Psychology program. Such a variety of reasons will be discussed further in this section. The most commonly cited reason is a passion for the profession, at 32%. This once more reflects an intrinsic motivation and interest among many people who pursue a career in psychology.

The second most cited reason, 24% of the respondents cited, was the course offering available in the chosen institution. This shows that accessibility and the offerings of the institutions were critical factors in choosing to take up studies, 8% of the respondents were inspired by a role model. This means that perhaps the input of coaches, teachers, or other influential people in the child's life has played a role. Other significant factors apart from the aforementioned are peer influence at 15% and parental or family influence at 13%, where social and family determinants manifest in educational decision-making processes. Furthermore, 17% stated that the program would lead to career development, and 10% said it is affordable for their family.

Less frequently mentioned reasons were direct employment promises (8%), good grades in high school (8%), and status or prestige of the profession (5%). A very small percentage, 3%, was motivated by a promise of attractive compensation; 4% mentioned that they would be able to work abroad. In addition, 6% of respondents

said they had no particular choice or no better idea for their course choice, and 5% said "other".

In conclusion, most respondents are guided by personal interest and considerations about accessibility and advancement opportunities at their workplaces. There is a high social factor and financial motivation; most are influenced by the family or peer pressure while making these decisions.

Table 6

Distribution of Respondents by the Training(s) and/or advanced studies they attended after college

Number of Attending Seminars/Training	Counts	% of Total
No	79	79.0 %
Yes	21	21.0 %
Training/Course		
Applied Behavioral Analysis Training	1	4.76
RBT Training	1	4.76
Orientation on Mental Health Act and Informed Consent	1	4.76
Labor Relations 101	1	4.76
HR Related Training	1	4.76
Juris Doctor Candidate	1	4.76
Certified Project Management Associate and Certified Lean Six Sigma Yellow Belt	1	4.76
Psychological First Aid	1	4.76
Master of Arts in Psychology	1	4.76
Technical and Business Report Writing, Enhancing Customer Service Excellence, Competency-Based Human Resource Management System- Job Description Writing	1	4.76
Mental Health's MH I Talk " Facing Our Greatest Enemy: The Guaranteed Method of Overcoming Impostor Syndrome "	1	4.76
Certified Human Resource Associate	10	47.62
Total	21	100%

The data in Table 6 depicts the spread of respondents based on the fact that they have participated in seminars, training programs, or advanced studies after college. As many as 79% of respondents indicated they had never attended further

training or advanced studies. In this regard, only 21% of the respondents mentioned that they had been engaged in such activities. In other words, it depicts that most graduates have not yet been involved in further education or professional development after completing their undergraduate degree.

Among those seeking further learning, twelve specific courses or training programs were specified and thus represent 21% of the whole group pursuing further studies. These courses covered various topics in Applied Behavioral Analysis Training, RBT Training, Orientation on the Mental Health Act, and Informed Consent, which all fall under psychology. Other courses that reflect my interests are Labor Relations 101, training in Human Resource-related studies, and a Certified Project Management Associate and Lean Six Sigma Yellow Belt. One other respondent is studying for her Juris Doctor degree; another respondent is a graduate of a Master's program in Arts in Psychology. Training in Psychological First Aid was another course listed. Some attended trainings i.e., Mental Health's MH I Talk "Facing Our Greatest Enemy: The Guaranteed Method of Overcoming Impostor Syndrome" and Technical and Business Report Writing, Enhancing Customer Service Excellence, Competency-Based Human Resource Management System- Job Description Writing. Lastly, 10 out of 21 respondents passed the Certified Human Resource Associate assessment examination.

This data reflects a diverse yet limited engagement in further studies or training, reflecting varying career paths and interests among the respondents. While some graduates have pursued opportunities to specialize or expand their skill sets, the vast majority have not yet taken steps toward formal advanced education or professional certifications. This may reflect financial or time constraints, a focus on gaining work experience, or limited awareness of the benefits of continuing education.

Table 7

Distribution of Respondents by the reason(s) for pursuing training(s) and/or advanced studies

Reasons for pursuing Training	Counts	% of Total
For Promotion, For Professional Development	3	14.29 %
For Professional Development	17	80.95 %
Interested to the topic	1	4.76 %
Total	21	100%

Table 7 Reports on the reasons for undertaking training and/or advanced studies after college According to respondents of the 21 who went for additional training or studies, the majority 80.95 percent or 17, cited professional development as the main reason. This highlights the need to build skills and knowledge in their areas of practice as the most compelling factor.

Meanwhile, 3 respondents said they were training for promotion and professional development. This means that career opportunities were a secondary motivator besides skill building. Last, 1 respondent was interested in the topic as the only reason to attend further training or studies. This reflects intrinsic motivation and personal curiosity in the subject matter.

The general data shows that overall professional development, career advancement, or skill improvement is still the major reason behind those students' decisions to undertake extra training or further study. A smaller group mentions being interested in some special topic. These observations, among others, explain that, for better graduates in further careers, all courses offered should be tailored around the needs of those entering higher education to fulfill professional development aspirations.

Table 8

Distribution of Respondents by Employment Incidence

Are you presently employed?	Counts	% of Total
Yes	87	87.0 %
Never Employed	6	6.0 %
No, but was previously employed	7	7.0 %
Total	100	100%

Table 8 illustrates data on the employment incidence of respondents. A total of 87 respondents are employed. This indicates that a great proportion of graduates have succeeded in the labor market transition.

Whereas 6 respondents, which equates to 6% stated they have never worked at any time in their life; this represents a relatively minimal percentage of the graduates, who might either have problems entering the job market, are still searching for available opportunities, or are focusing on furthering their studies. Meanwhile, 7 respondents (7%) reported that they are currently not working, although they used to work at some point. These will mostly represent individuals, who would have quit working for various reasons like taking other courses, job hopping, or even for other personal reasons. Overall, the data indicates that the employment outcome for the majority of respondents is quite strong because most of the graduates are currently working.

Table 9

Distribution of Unemployed but Previously Employed Respondents by Reason for Unemployment

Reasons for Unemployment	Counts	% of Total
No job opportunity	1	14.3 %
Family concern and decided not to find a job, Did not look for a job	1	14.3 %
Waiting for the response from my applications	1	14.3 %
Health-related reason(s)	1	14.3 %
Switching from industrial to clinical facet of the profession	1	14.3 %
Advance or further study, Did not look for a job	1	14.3 %
Advance or further study, Preparing for graduate school application	1	14.3 %
Total	7	100%

Table 9 Details of reasons for unemployment from respondents who were once employed Total number of respondents who were once employed and had a reason for being unemployed 7 Each had a different reason for the reason for unemployment, hence all accounting for 14.3%.

Some respondents mentioned the following external factors that led to their unemployment. One person mentioned that there are no job opportunities, while another said they are awaiting a response from job applications. These reasons relate to problems in the labor market or recruitment procedures that might delay re-employment.

Other respondents identified personal or situational reasons such as family issues, which would force them to decline to find a job, or health reasons, which would prevent them from being able to work. The last respondent said they are leaving the industry to join the clinical facet of the profession, and they need time to adapt skills and licensure in the clinical domain.

Finally, two respondents also had as the main reason they would not be seeking work advancement or further study plans, and one of those is particularly preparing to apply to graduate school. Such respondents focus on developing themselves both academically and professionally instead of returning to the workplace immediately.

It goes without saying that the factors behind unemployment for these respondents are diverse, ranging from external job market challenges, personal circumstances, and even career development goals. All this diversity requires targeted support to address the individual challenge, whether in providing job placement assistance, career counseling, or the pathway to further education and skill development.

Table 10*Distribution of Never Employed Respondents by Reason for Unemployment*

Reasons for Unemployment	Counts	% of Total
No job opportunity	1	16.7 %
Have applied but waiting for a job interview.	1	16.7 %
Did not look for a job	2	33.3 %
Advanced or further study	1	16.7 %
Family concerned and decided not to find a job	1	16.7 %
Total	6	100%

The reasons for unemployment among the 6 individuals who have never worked, according to Table 10 are as follows. The most common reason among them is that they never looked for a job and thus may be because of personal choices, other priorities, or external circumstances in 2 respondents or 33.3%.

The remaining respondents accounted for 16.7% of the total, each citing different reasons for their unemployment. One respondent pointed out that there is a lack of job opportunities, which may be a problem in finding appropriate employment in the job market. Another respondent stated that they have applied but are waiting for a job interview, implying that their unemployment is only temporary and due to the recruitment process.

Other reasons are to advance or pursue further studies, which indicates an interest in academic or professional development before entering the labor market. Another respondent stated family concerns and a decision not to find a job, which may indicate personal circumstances that limit their ability or willingness to seek employment.

Table 11*Distribution of Respondents by Present Employment Status*

Employment Status	Counts	% of Total
Regular or Permanent	74	78.7 %
Contractual	12	12.8 %
Temporary	3	3.2 %
Casual	1	1.1 %
Self-employed	4	4.3 %
Total	94	100%

Data in Table 11, the current employment status of 94 currently working respondents, shows that 74 respondents, or 78.7 percent, hold regular or permanent posts, reflecting stable employment for most employed graduates. This percentage

indicates a great degree of integration into stable employment roles for most of the respondents.

On the other hand, 12 respondents (12.8%) are contractors, which is a smaller percentage of employees whose jobs could be fixed-term or even project-based. Then 3 respondents (3.2%) were in a temporary position, and 1 respondent (1.1%) was in casual employment, which is a portion of less secure or not permanent status.

Besides that, 4 respondents, 4.3%, had themselves as self-employed people; these are entrepreneurial pursuits or independent professional work; therefore, it shows a proportion of graduates who may have chosen or transitioned to become self-employed in terms of career paths that diversify.

In summary, the data depicts that the majority of respondents who were working were in regular or permanent employment, therefore some form of employment security exists. This, however, also provides evidence for people's occupation in positions such as contractual, temporary, casual, or self-employed positions, and at least among such groups in rather insecure work arrangements, one can postulate work experience and support or development areas.

Table 12

Distribution of Respondents by the Relatedness of Psychology to Their Profession

Is your current job related to Psychology?	Counts	% of Total
Yes	41	71.9 %
No	16	28.1 %
Total	57	100%

The data in Table 12 shows the alignment of current jobs and fields of study in psychology. The respondents to the question are individuals whose current job is their first employment experience; excluding those who already have previous employment. In general, from the total respondents of 57 incorporated in the analysis, 41 respondents, or 71.9%, say their current job is a psychologist, thus meaning a considerable majority found relevant employment upon completion of their education background. That is, most of the respondents could find relevant career paths upon completion of their training in psychology. This is supported by the study of Anderson, P. H., & Lawton, L. (2015), which indicates that if the university's curricula closely align with the industry demands, it will positively affect the employability of its graduates.

On the contrary, 16 respondents, or 28.1%, believe their present work is unrelated to psychology. This is a huge percentage of graduates who have probably done other fields because their professional interests cut across fields, there are few openings in careers related to psychology, and there are more career prospects in those fields.

In conclusion, the data shows that despite the fact that a great majority of the respondents work in psychology-related jobs, a significant number have been employed in other fields. This indicates that psychology graduates are versatile and can adjust to various professional roles; it also calls for knowledge of the factors that shape career choices and their association with academic preparation.

Table 13

Distribution of Respondents by Reasons for Accepting the Jobs

Factor	Counts	Percentage of Total
Salaries and Benefits	10	27.0%
Related to special skills	9	24.3%
Proximity to residence	7	18.9%
Career Challenge	8	21.6%
Ideal job for me	1	2.7%
Since I mentioned that I'm transitioning...	1	2.7%
For experience	1	2.7%
Total	37	100%

The findings of Table 13 illustrate the main reasons given by respondents for taking their current jobs. In all, 37 respondents said that salaries and benefits (10 or 27.0%) were why they accepted their jobs, meaning financial recompense and security form important bases for making job-related decisions. This is supported by the study of Koh, S. L., & Nair, M. (2020), which found that the more influential factor that influences the younger generation to accept job offers is the compensation packages offered by the company since they view the package as indicators of long-term stability and growth opportunities.

From the findings, the critical factors influencing job acceptance were found to be the money offered, relevance to competencies, and vicinity of their home. Additionally, career progression and self-satisfaction significantly influence a job's decision, proving job choices to be rather diversified. It is thereby revealed that this diversity must be addressed while supporting the graduates so that the results will not be undesirable after such placements.

Table 14

Distribution of Respondents by How Long It Took the Respondents to Land on their First Job

	Counts	% of Total
Less than a month	43	45.7 %
2 months	1	1.1 %
1 week after passing 2024 Blepp	1	1.1 %
1 to 6 months	44	46.8 %

	Counts	% of Total
7 to 11 months	1	1.1 %
Before graduation	1	1.1 %
1 year to less than 2 years	1	1.1 %
After I quit my training as a Casino Dealer, I took a break for a month. And after a month, I decided to search for an HR position. It took me almost 3 weeks on search, then decided to why not try CSR position while still searching for an opportunity to come.	1	1.1 %
Ive been working here even before graduating	1	1.1 %
Total	94	100%

The findings in Table 14 can be interpreted regarding the period it took them to gain their first job after leaving college. In this respect, of the 94 respondents, a majority of 44 students (46.8 percent) stated that they achieved their first job within 1-6 months, thus evidencing a relatively rapid transition to employment for most graduates. Another significant share, 43 respondents (45.7%), found their first job within less than a month, which further reiterates the effectiveness with which a significant share of the graduates entered the workforce.

Smaller shares of respondents reported longer periods before gaining employment. A total of 1.1% each of the respondents took 7 to 11 months, 1 year less than 2 years, or were employed prior to graduation. This diversity is best depicted in the job search process. Others have elaborated on their personal experiences, such as breaks before the actual job hunting and trial and error periods, like leaving a casino dealer training course for a position as CSR.

The data indicates that a minority of graduates experienced longer timelines, likely due to personal decisions, market conditions, or career exploration. These findings highlight the general readiness of graduates to enter the workforce promptly while also reflecting individual differences in employment pathways.

Table 15

Distribution of Respondents by Job Level Position (First Job)

First Job	Counts	% of Total
Rank and file	60	66.3 %
Professional, Technical, Supervisory	18	20.2 %
HR Assistant	1	1.1 %
Specialist	1	1.1 %

First Job	Counts	% of Total
Managerial or Executive	2	2.2 %
Self-employed	2	2.2 %
Trainee	1	1.1 %
Contractual	2	2.2 %
Junior Behavior Therapist	1	1.1 %
Entry-level	1	1.1 %
Total	89	100%

Table 15 breaks down the distribution of respondents according to their job level positions in their first job. Of the 89 respondents, the majority of them, 59 persons or 66.3%, started their careers in rank-and-file jobs, which means that most graduates enter the workforce for the first time in entry-level jobs that require core skills. Jackson, D. (2015) stated that fresh graduates were more likely to start in lower-level jobs because employers often prioritize work experience over academic qualifications Neumark, D., & Shirley, P. (2022) also found that graduates without professional experience often struggled to secure high-level positions due to their experience.

Another important group, 18 respondents (20.2%), began as professionals, technical, or supervisory; this implies that some of the graduates were able to find positions with greater levels of responsibility and specialized expertise. Small percentages of the respondents held other types of positions: managerial or executive (2.2%), self-employed (2.2%), and contractual employment (2.2%); again, these results indicate diverse entry points.

More exclusive positions include an HR Assistant, Specialist, Junior Behavior Therapist, Entry-level, and many more which add up to 1.1% of the overall respondents. This demonstrates a large number of options for a graduate's career path; however, the majority still hold clerical and professional positions.

In conclusion, the data shows that even though most graduates start out in rank-and-file positions, a large number of graduates also enter higher, more specialized, or supervisory positions. Such a distribution reflects the ability of psychology graduates to find work in a wide variety of jobs and industries at all levels. The prevalence of managerial, self-employed, and other categories indicates that there are many diverse types of opportunities for graduates based on their skills, interests, and professional goals.

Table 16*Distribution of Respondents by Job Level Position (Current Job)*

Current Job	Counts	% of Total
rank and file	45	50.6 %
Professional, Technical, Supervisory	31	34.8 %
HR Assistant	1	1.1 %
Specialist	1	1.1 %
Managerial or Executive	3	3.4 %
n/a	1	1.1 %
Trainee	1	1.1 %
Contractual	1	1.1 %
Senior Behavior Therapist	1	1.1 %
Self-employed	3	3.4 %
Entry-level	1	1.1 %
Total	89	100%

Data from Table 16 shows the distribution of respondents by current job level position. Of the 89 respondents, 45 or 50.6% are in rank/clerical positions, which is still the most common job level. Nonetheless, this percentage is smaller than in their first jobs at 66.3%, indicating career advancement in some of the respondents.

There is a high increase in the percentage of respondents who are currently professionals, technical, or supervisors, 31 respondents, 34.8%, in these positions as compared to 20.2% in their first jobs. This shows that there is career advancement and development of skills among many of the respondents over time. The increase in the number of respondents whose job level advances after their first job is supported by the study of Tomlinson, M. (2021), which found that most graduates use their first job as a stepping stone in order to secure promotions or better job offers in the market. Findings also indicate that first jobs often provide graduates with initial experience that will enable them to reach higher-level positions.

Overall, the data appears to show that, although respondents largely remain in ranks or clerical positions, there is an important phenomenon of upward mobility as most of them can now be seen in growing numbers in professional and supervisory positions. These trends indicate the possible career advances of psychology graduates. Other distributions across levels of various jobs also highlight the resilience and flexibility of graduates adapting to different types of industries and roles.

Table 17*Distribution of Respondents by Initial Gross Monthly Income*

Gross Monthly Income	Counts	% of Total
₱15,000 to less than ₱20,000	41	43.6 %
₱20,000 to less than ₱25,000	17	18.1 %
₱5,000 to less than ₱10,000	7	7.4 %
₱10,000 to less than ₱15,000	13	13.8 %
₱25,000 and above	16	17.0 %
Total	94	100%

Table 17 presents information on the distribution of the respondents according to their opening gross monthly income. The largest group, 41 out of 94 (43.6%), are those who earn between ₱15,000 to less than ₱20,000, thus revealing this range as the starting salary most commonly given for the graduates.

The total number of respondents shows that about 79% of the respondents had an initial monthly income of ₱10,000 or more, and more than one-third of the respondents had a monthly income of between ₱15,000 and ₱20,000. It mirrors the diversified earning capabilities of graduates, which could be determined by job position, industry, and location. This indicates that for most graduates, there is scope for competitive starting salaries. At the same time, a smaller number would begin on lower wages, probably in entry-level jobs or certain industries that are known to have lower salary scales. Pernia, E. M., & Balisacan, A. M. (2020) explained that the large pool of graduates in the Philippines annually results in limited demand for entry-level jobs; hence, the oversupply of graduates resort to available jobs that offer salaries on the lower end, i.e., ₱15,000 to ₱20,000 range.

Table 18*Distribution of Respondents by the Relevance of the Curriculum to Their First Job*

Relevance of the Curriculum to their first job	Counts	% of Total
No	26	27.7 %
Yes	68	72.3 %
Total	100	100%

The findings in Table 18 show the extent to which the curriculum offered at school was relevant to the respondents' first job. Among the respondents, most, that is, 68 (72.3%), found that their curriculum was relevant to their first job. Such a high

percentage highlights that there was a correspondence between the kind of academic preparation given through the Psychology program and the needs of most jobs. This may suggest that the curriculum appropriately readied the students for employment.

On the other hand, 26 respondents (27.7%) felt that their curriculum was irrelevant to their first job. This percentage points to some of the graduates whose entry-level jobs might not have directly fallen within the domain of the training they received in university, probably due to being employed in unrelated areas or jobs that demanded general skills rather than specialized knowledge in psychology. Van Noy, M., & Cleary, J. (2017) stated that aligning undergraduate education with the job market's needs and demands is essential for graduates' employability, especially in the early stages of their careers. Career and undergraduate program alignment is one of the factors that affected the high employment rate of the graduates.

In conclusion, the data shows that the curriculum is very relevant for most of the respondents' first jobs, thus supporting successful transitions into roles that fit the academic training.

Table 19

Relevance of courses offered in the curriculum of the Psychology program at Rizal Technological University to the respondents' job

Subjects	Mean	SD	Verbal Interpretation
Experimental Psychology	2.11	1.01	Somewhat Relevant
General Chemistry	1.31	0.704	Not Relevant
General Zoology	1.26	0.655	Not Relevant
Genetic Science	1.48	0.889	Not Relevant
Biological Science	1.46	0.825	Not Relevant
Developmental Psychology	2.73	1.228	Relevant
Biological Psychology	1.88	1.076	Somewhat Relevant
Psychological Statistics	2.52	1.143	Relevant
Labor Law	3	1.2	Relevant
Filipino Psychology	1.99	1.102	Somewhat Relevant
Abnormal Psychology	2.21	1.235	Somewhat Relevant
Cognitive Psychology	2.63	1.164	Relevant
Thesis Writing	2.03	1.092	Somewhat Relevant
Social Psychology	3.02	1.107	Relevant
Industrial/Organizational Psychology	3.37	1.037	Very Relevant
Psychological Assessment	2.66	1.232	Relevant

Strategic Human Resource	2.95	1.23	Relevant
Human Behavior in Organization	3.17	1.161	Relevant
Group Dynamics	3.07	1.203	Relevant
Positive Psychology	2.87	1.138	Relevant
Research in Psychology	2.13	1.09	Somewhat Relevant
Pagbasa ng mga Dalumat sa Pilipino tungo sa Pananaliksik	1.47	0.799	Not Relevant
Introduction to Psychology	2.07	1.109	Somewhat Relevant
Field Method in Psychology	1.96	1.106	Somewhat Relevant
Theories of Personality	2.36	1.172	Somewhat Relevant
Introduction to Clinical Psychology	2.03	1.102	Somewhat Relevant
Disaster and Mental Health	2.41	1.213	Somewhat Relevant
Cooperative Education in Industry (Industrial Setting)	2.72	1.299	Relevant
Cooperative Education in Industry (Clinical Setting)	1.93	1.109	Somewhat Relevant
Seminar in Psychology	2.2	1.266	Somewhat Relevant
Overall Average	2.30	1.090	Somewhat Relevant

Note: "1.00-1.75 Not Relevant", "1.76-2.50 Somewhat Relevant", "2.51-3.25 Relevant", "3.26-4.00 Very Relevant"

The results presented in Table 19 give information regarding the relevance of the Rizal Technological University Psychology program curriculum on the respondents' work. Courses such as Group Dynamics (3.07), Industrial/Organizational Psychology (3.37), and Strategic Human Resource (2.95) are marked as "Relevant", which indicates that these courses fit well in working situations mainly in industrial or organizational sectors. This gives the conclusion that such classes have apt relevance to graduates' working lives, specifically for workforces that belong to related psychology professions.

Further, subjects such as General Chemistry (1.31), General Zoology (1.28), and Genetic Science (1.48) are rated as "Not Relevant." This implies that certain aspects of the curriculum have limited relevance to respondents' current job positions. This result is affected by the low representativeness of Rizal Technological University Psychology graduates who are either in or preparing to be in the educational and clinical setting of Psychology. The selected respondents, who are mostly working in the industrial setting of Psychology, viewed the Science-related courses as somewhat not relevant to their current job.

The results are supported by several studies that are related to this. For instance, Camuyong, C. S. F., Decena, C. F., Reyes, K. C., Malong, M. R., Gregorio,

M. C. L., Magtalas, S. A., & Adlawan, J. E. (2023) conducted a study in which it was discovered that 67% of psychology graduates believed that the undergraduate degree was relevant for employment. The development of the communication and collaborative skills of graduates has been critical in their careers. Similarly, the Albina, A. C., & Sumagaysay, L. P. (2020) study highlighted that 69.78% of IT graduates found their college program relevant to their first jobs. These findings point to the importance of academic programs being industry-need-driven for employability purposes.

In addition, research conducted by Senekal, J. S., & Smith, M. R. (2022), highlighted graduate tracer studies on the appropriateness of education about labor-market demands. Their research proved that an important part of the graduates of psychology had entered occupations that are close to the study domain, such as health and education, the implication of which was to ensure the curriculum relevance about employability.

Table 20

The usefulness of Competencies Developed in Psychology Program to the Respondents' Job

Competencies	Mean	SD	Verbal Interpretation
Interpersonal Communication	3.82	0.439	Extremely Useful
Conflict Management	3.67	0.575	Extremely Useful
Resiliency	3.67	0.612	Extremely Useful
Technological Competence	3.68	0.608	Extremely Useful
Decision-making	3.76	0.543	Extremely Useful
Active Listening	3.87	0.394	Extremely Useful
Strategic Planning	3.65	0.581	Extremely Useful
Industry Knowledge	3.69	0.704	Extremely Useful
Adaptability and agility	3.85	0.439	Extremely Useful
Overall Average	3.74	0.544	Extremely Useful

The data in Table 20 evaluates the usefulness of competencies developed in the Psychology program to the respondents' jobs. Based on the mean scores, all competencies listed were rated as "Extremely Useful," with an overall average of 3.74. The highest-rated competencies were Adaptability and Agility (3.85) and Active Listening (3.87), reflecting their critical importance in professional settings, particularly in roles requiring flexibility and effective communication.

Other competencies, Interpersonal Communication (3.82), Decision-making (3.76), and Technological Competence (3.68), further reflect the significant importance with their application within the respondents' workplace, showing that skills like Conflict Management (3.67), Resiliency (3.67), Strategic Planning (3.65), and Industry Knowledge (3.69) further relate to the universal applicability of the skills developed while undertaking the Psychology program and are therefore worth applying irrespective of the different job requirements and industries involved.

These are consistent with the findings of Balah, K. O. (2023), who has cited that psychology courses do significantly develop the graduates' problem-solving, communication, and academic skills; therefore, they add to them professionally. Similar to what Peña, R., Buenaventura, N., Formacion, I. J., & Dino, R. J. (2022) discussed, a program such as the Master of Arts in Filipino at the Polytechnic University of the Philippines had been designed correctly to orient the trainees to appropriate professional skills and values wherein, they will be able to become productive employees.

Another study by Basir, N. M., Zubairi, Y. Z., Jani, R., & Wahab, D. A. (2022) found the key competencies that improve employability to be teamwork, problem-solving, and confidence in their practice. This paper's findings align with that notion, indicating that the graduates should be better prepared to meet the dynamic needs of the labor market, acquiring competencies such as Adaptability, Interpersonal Communication, and Active Listening.

Meto, R. (2023) found that there was a high utilization of cognitive, emotional, and psychomotor skills in graduates of education programs in their professions that support the necessity for a curriculum that balances technical skills and soft skills. Similarly, Sayson, C. J. O., Asilum, W. G., Pintacasi, J. E., Pepania, A. D., & Sumicad Jr, E. H. (2024) emphasized that undergraduate programs help develop important skills for professional development and found the same results with this study regarding how competencies such as Strategic Planning and Decision-making were highly significant.

Indeed, the competencies developed from the Psychology program at Rizal Technological University proved very useful for graduates' careers, for they received "Extremely Useful" ratings. Similarly, numerous tracer studies further support this finding, affirming that higher education institutions play a critical role in preparing students for the competencies necessary for success on the job. To sustain and develop the latter, institutions must continue prioritizing the inclusion of the above competencies in their curriculum, but with ongoing feedback solicitation from the graduates that their curricula are abreast with industry demands change over time.

Table 21

The usefulness of skills developed in the Psychology Program to the Respondents' Job

Developed Skills	Mean	SD	Verbal Interpretation
Human Relations Skills	3.83	0.455	Extremely Useful

Problem-Solving Skills	3.81	0.422	Extremely Useful
Critical Thinking Skills	3.86	0.347	Extremely Useful
Organizing Skills	3.8	0.499	Extremely Useful
Leadership Skills	3.55	0.728	Extremely Useful
Work Ethic Skills	3.89	0.343	Extremely Useful
Research Skills	3.36	0.902	Extremely Useful
Overall Average	3.73	0.528	Extremely Useful

Table 21 shows the degree of usefulness of skills learned in the Psychology program to jobs. All the skills listed here were rated "Extremely Useful," with a general average of 3.73. The highest-rated skill was Work Ethic Skills at 3.89, followed closely by Critical Thinking Skills and Human Relations Skills at 3.86 and 3.83, respectively, indicating that these competencies are very important in the workplace.

Other skills with a high rating include Problem-Solving Skills at 3.81, Organizing Skills at 3.80, and Leadership Skills at 3.55. These ratings indicate the program's success in imparting transferable skills that enable participants to perform effectively at work. Research Skills, with a score of 3.36, is rated as "Extremely Useful" but in very narrow roles or tasks requiring the skills of investigation and analysis.

These results agree with the study done by Esparrago, M. (2022), which indicates that the skills and knowledge learned during this course have contributed significantly to professional improvement. The respondent could credit most of his or her career success at different levels, including local, regional, national, and international levels, for his or her competencies developed. Likewise, all these skills are basic in professional advancement and personal development.

The good ratings for the critical skills in the study are also consistent with Basir, N. M., Zubairi, Y. Z., Jani, R., & Wahab, D. A. (2022), which pointed to the fact that communication, teamwork, and problem-solving skills were the most critical employability factors. Also, Meto, R. (2023) pointed out that cognitive, psychomotor, and affective skills are relevant to professional practice and are on par with the wide array of skills evaluated in the study.

In a nutshell, the skills learned in the Psychology program of Rizal Technological University are very useful and could be applied directly to jobs by the respondents. The results of the study give assurance that the program does have the capability to prepare its graduates to perform effectively within their job environment as well as to make worthwhile contributions to their organizations and communities. Moreover, by continuing to nurture and refine these competencies, the program can work towards ensuring that graduates are prepared for the changing demands of the labor market.

Table 22*ANOVA - Competencies*

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	p	Decision on Ho	Interpretation
Developed Skills	86.64	10	8.6643	133	< .001	Rejected	There is a significant difference in the developed skills and learned competencies of the respondents in the psychology program when grouped according to their employment Status.
Residuals	5.79	89	0.0650				

The ANOVA table analyzes the variation in skills developed by respondents in the psychology program and tests whether such variations are statistically significant. It indicates that the sum of squares for developed skills is 86.64, with a mean square value of 8.6643. Residuals accounted for a smaller sum of squares, 5.79, with a mean square value of 0.0650.

The F-statistic is 133, and the p-value is less than 0.001. Therefore, a statistically significant result. It means that the perceived contributions of the developed skills to the respondents' job performance or relevance vary significantly.

The outcomes suggest some skills are far more paramount than others concerning perceived applicability in the working world. The high F-statistic points to how various effects of different skills are likely to have in making a job applicant employable and to perform well at work like most other relevant studies, including Esparrago, M. (2022), which pointed to human capital as a determining factor to professional success and community impacts.

In conclusion, the ANOVA results confirm that skills learned through the Psychology program vary considerably in applicability and impact, confirming the program's effectiveness in preparing its graduates with competencies that meaningfully contribute to professional success. More in-depth analysis could also pinpoint which specific skills influence the statistical significance and give recommendations on how to enhance the curriculum.

4. Discussion

The respondents of this study were the 2021 to 2023 Rizal Technological University Psychology Graduates. The total population of both Boni and Pasig campuses' psychology graduates from batches 2021-2023 was eight hundred and thirty-eight (838) graduates, and the researchers were able to draw and reach a sample size of one hundred (100) psychology graduates. The researchers utilized Google Forms as their medium for the survey questionnaire. The researchers utilized Facebook, Messenger, Gmail, and LinkedIn to reach their respondents. The study's findings showed that 61% of the respondents were from the Pasig campus, most of them female and single in civil status, currently residing in cities, and from the batch 2022.

The results of the study showed that 99% of the respondents attained a Bachelor's degree, received awards, i.e., Cum Laude, Dean's Lister, etc. during their undergraduate program, most, 56%, have not yet passed any professional examinations, most are still in preparation to take an examination, others may be placed in careers where no exam is necessary, or some who wants experience over accreditation, the majority took the psychology program because of their strong passion for the profession, and 21 out of 100 respondents have attended training and advanced studies after college for professional development.

Further, the results of the study also showed that 21% of the respondents had attended training and/or advanced studies, i.e., Applied Behavioral Analysis Training, RBT Training, Orientation on Mental Health Act and Informed Consent, Labor Relations 101, HR-Related Training, Juris Doctor, Certified Project Management Associate and Certified Lean Six Sigma, Yellow Belt, Psychological First Aid, Master of Arts in Psychology, Certified Human Resource Associate after college for promotion and professional development.

Employment Data of the Respondents

Moreover, the results of the study also showed that 87% of the respondents are currently employed, 78.7% are regular or permanent in their profession, 31.9% of the respondents are working as professionals, 91.5% are working locally, most of them accepted their job because of its relatedness to their special skills and stays in their job because of the salaries and benefits their company provides, 71.9% of the respondents are working within the field of Psychology, mostly in the industrial, most of their job level is rank and file, 42.9% of the respondents earn at least PHP 15,000 to less than PHP 20,000 monthly.

Based on the findings of the study, 72.3% of the respondents agreed that the curriculum the Psychology program at Rizal Technological University provides is relevant to their job; Industrial/Organizational Psychology is found to be the most relevant course offered by the Psychology program to the respondents' job mainly because most of the respondents are working in the industrial setting of psychology, it is also found that active listening and work ethic skills are the most useful and relevant skill and competencies the respondents developed after taking psychology program in Rizal Technological University when it comes to their job.

Lastly, based on the findings, some skills are far more paramount than others concerning perceived applicability in the working world. The high F-statistic points to the various effects of different skills that will likely make a job applicant employable and perform well at work. The skills learned through the Psychology program vary considerably in applicability and impact, confirming its effectiveness in preparing graduates with competencies that meaningfully contribute to professional success. Findings revealed a significant difference in the respondents' developed skills and learned competencies in the psychology program when they were grouped according to their employment status.

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